

MECHANISTIC INSIGHTS INTO THE CO₂ ACTIVATION ON METAL SURFACES

Luca Dietz¹, Simone Piccinin^{2*} and Matteo Maestri^{1**}

¹Laboratory of Catalysis and Catalytic Processes, Dipartimento di Energia - Politecnico di Milano,
Piazza Leonardo da Vinci 32, 20133 Milano, Italy

²CNR-IOM DEMOCRITOS c/o SISSA, Via Bonomea 265, 34136 Trieste, Italy

Corresponding authors:

Simone Piccinin: *piccinin@iom.cnr.it

Matteo Maestri: **matteo.maestri@polimi.it

ABSTRACT

By the means of DFT calculations, we find that CO₂ activation follows different elementary steps at the atomic scale on different metals (Pt, Rh, Ni, Ag, Cu, Pd). We relate these differences to the interactions between the adsorbed oxygen and the metals, which strongly affect the dissociation activation energy. In particular, CO₂ dissociation is favored on metals which present high affinity toward oxygen. As the O binding energy decreases, CO₂ hydrogenation becomes more favored at the expenses of the dissociation. Such findings allow to rationalize the different catalytic cycles reported in the literature for r-WGS on metal surfaces.

Key-words: CO₂ activation; r-WGS mechanism; DFT calculations; Rh; Pt; Ni; Ag; Cu; Pd.

Oil, natural gas and coal combustion processes, involved in power generation, are accountable for increasing CO₂ atmospheric concentration, which is considered to be one of the main causes of climate changes and global warming¹. Beside the environmental concern, CO₂ represents a highly functional and abundant chemical reagent for chemicals and fuels and could potentially be a renewable and environmentally friendly source of carbon. Therefore, upgrading CO₂ into more valuable products is considered as one of the most promising solutions for a CO₂-neutral energy supply. In this regard, cost-effective technologies are required to reduce CO₂ emissions², as well as approaches where CO₂ is converted into higher-value chemicals³ or used for the “chemical storage” of energy produced by renewable sources on a large scale⁴. In this respect, the chemical conversion of CO₂ is mainly achieved via hydrogenation to, e.g., CH₄, CH₃OH or CH₂O on metal based catalysts⁵⁻⁹. In these processes, a crucial issue is related to the high chemical stability of CO₂, which is hard to activate at high conversion rates and selectivity¹⁰. It is therefore of great importance to derive a detailed mechanistic understanding at the atomic scale in order to clarify the basic chemical processes of CO₂ activation, which encompasses the reverse water gas shift (r-WGS) reaction as first step on the metal surfaces. At present, despite an increasingly large number of investigations¹¹⁻²⁴, debates still exist on the reaction mechanism and elementary steps involved in the water gas shift (WGS) and r-WGS reaction pathways. In particular, for activation of CO₂ on metal catalysts, three different mechanisms have been proposed for the conversion of CO₂ to CO via a r-WGS route, characterized by the following key steps¹⁰:

The occurrence of different mechanisms is found to depend on the specific catalysts and operating conditions. In particular, Mavrikakis and co-workers^{11,12} suggested that a COOH-mediated mechanism is favored for the CO₂ hydrogenation on Pt catalysts, whereas Maestri and co-workers

found – in agreement with experimental kinetic investigations²⁵ – that r-WGS proceeds through the CO₂ dissociation mechanism on Rh^{22,26}. The formate (HCOO) mechanism – despite the fact that HCOO has been detected on the catalyst surface by the means of operando DRIFT and SSITKA analysis¹⁷ – is usually discarded, because of the high stability of HCOO on the surface, which makes HCOO a spectator rather than a reactive intermediate^{27–30}.

Understanding the reasons of the mechanistic differences among the metals is crucial in the effort to gain a mechanistic interpretation of CO₂ activation, and detailed analysis by theory are required to link such different prevalent mechanisms on the metals to specific properties at the atomic scale. In view of this, we present a detailed DFT analysis of the dissociation mechanism (CO₂ → CO+O) and the COOH-mediated mechanism for the r-WGS on (111) surfaces of Rh, Pt, Ni, Ag, Cu and Pd. We show that the tendency of the different catalysts to promote different catalytic cycles is ultimately related to their affinity to oxygen. In particular, as O binding energy increases, the COOH-mediated mechanism becomes dominant at the expenses of the dissociation mechanism. As a consequence, the dominant reaction path changes among the metals and, in turn, a unique catalyst descriptor cannot be identified.

All DFT calculations presented in this work are performed with the Quantum ESPRESSO code³¹, based on plane waves, and ultrasoft pseudo-potentials. The exchange and correlation potential is approximated using the GGA-PBE functional^{32,33}. Kohn-Sham states are expanded in a basis set of plane waves with a cutoff of 40 Ry and a 6x6x1 Monkhorst-Pack grid is used to sample the Brillouin zone. This set of parameters was verified to ensure the numerical convergence within 30 meV of the computed binding energies. The (111) metal surfaces are modeled with a periodically repeated slab geometry, using a 2x2 surface unit cell, four atomic layers and a vacuum spacing of 12 Å. The first three layers are fixed at the atomic bulk position, whereas the fourth layer is allowed to relax. Adsorption is allowed only on one side of the slab. Binding energies are computed as difference between the adsorption system and the sum of the energy of the clean metal slab and the

total energy of the gas phase molecules. Spin-polarized calculations are employed for gas phase molecules as well as for the Ni surfaces, which display a ferromagnetic behavior³⁴. Activation energies are computed by the means of the Climbing Image – Nudged Elastic Band (CI-NEB) method³⁵, using 12 images and a convergence criterion on forces of 0.1 eV/Å. Since the GGA-PBE functional does not describe van der Waals interactions, we used the Grimme approach³⁶ to evaluate their influence on the activation energies. As reported in the Supplemental Information, inclusion of dispersion interactions leads to a slight and almost rigid shift of all activation energies, without significantly altering their relative magnitude. All values reported in the main text do not include the Grimme correction.

We start with the analysis of the dissociation and COOH-mediated mechanisms on Pt and Rh (111) surfaces (Figure 1). Details on the elementary steps included in the two mechanisms are reported in Table 1. For additional information on the reaction pathways, we refer the reader to the Supplemental Information.

FIGURE 1

In the case of Pt (Figure 1a), upon adsorption of CO₂ and H₂ at the surface, the hydrogenation of CO₂ to trans-COOH turns out to be more favorable than the dissociation of CO₂ (0.92 eV Vs. 1.66 eV), in agreement with what reported also by Mavrikakis and co-workers¹¹. In the case of Rh (Figure 1b), instead, the dissociation route prevails, because it exhibits an activation energy considerably lower than the one needed for the formation of the trans-COOH (0.77 eV Vs. 1.07 eV). In particular, on one side, the barrier for the formation of trans-COOH is not markedly affected by the metal (0.92 eV and 1.07 eV for Pt and Rh, respectively). On the other side, a remarkable decrement of the barrier for the CO₂ dissociation is predicted (1.66 eV and 0.77 eV for Pt and Rh, respectively). Such a change is crucial in enabling two different mechanisms for CO₂ activation on the two metals as reported in Figure 1a and Figure 1b.

FIGURE 2

Figure 2 reports the comparison between the dissociation and hydrogenation activation barriers for all the six investigated metals. On one side, Ni and Cu show a behavior similar to Rh, with the dissociation route favored on the hydrogenation one. On the other side, Ag and Pd surfaces are similar to Pt and the hydrogenation route turns out to be energetically favored with respect to dissociation one. We now aim to rationalize such a trend among the metals and to relate it to specific properties at the atomistic level, which can then be eventually used to identify a proper catalyst descriptor. To this end, we first focus our attention on the CO₂ dissociation reaction.

As previously reported in the literature^{37,38}, CO₂ displays a weak interaction with all the metal surfaces. Starting from CO₂ as initial state, we computed the minimum energy path for the dissociation into CO and O adsorbed in neighboring top and fcc sites of the (111) surface, respectively. For Pt, Rh and Ni metal surfaces we found the reaction to proceed through a metastable intermediate with positive adsorption energy, where CO₂ is bent and the C-O bonds stretched.

FIGURE 3

As Figure 3 clearly shows, the geometry of the transition state is nearly identical for all the metals. The transition state (TS) of the reaction is characterized by a fully cleaved C-O bond, and a second C-O bond that in all cases is almost identical to the value for the CO molecule in the final state (~1.15 Å). At the TS, the O atom is in a bridge position, while the CO molecule is slightly tilted and displaced away from the hollow site towards the top site. In spite of very similar geometries, the activation energy for this reaction is remarkably different on the six metals, from 0.77 eV for Rh to 2.86 eV for Ag.

FIGURE 4

The reaction obeys the Brønsted-Evans-Polanyi (BEP) relation³⁹⁻⁴¹, since there is a linear relationship between the activation energy and the energy of reaction as shown in Figure 4. From the magnitude of the linear coefficient in Figure 4 (0.71), we can infer that the TS for this step is of

late character, consistent with the geometries shown in Figure 3 and with the fact that the binding energy of CO₂ (the initial state of this reaction) is very similar and weak on all the metals. Therefore, the energy of the TS is strongly influenced by the energy of the final state. In this respect, we found that the trends in the activation energy of the dissociation can be related to the different trends of the CO and O binding energies according to Eq. (1):

$$E_{diss} = 0.73E_{be,O} + 0.43E_{be,CO} + 5.61 \quad (1)$$

where $E_{be,O}$ and $E_{be,CO}$ are the binding energies expressed in eV of O and CO, respectively. From Eq. (1), it is evident that the dissociation energy is mainly affected by O-metal interaction. Yet, CO has a non-negligible effect. This is particularly true for Cu and Ag, which are characterized by a remarkable destabilization of the CO on the surface with respect to the other four metals (see Table 2). As a consequence, any sort of destabilization suffered by O and CO on the surface has a direct effect upon the capability of the system to dissociate CO₂ into CO and O, and thus operating conditions, which determine the surface coverage, dramatically act upon kinetic parameters according to Eq. (1)⁴². Noticeably, given the fact that the lattice parameters of the metals differ substantially, lateral interactions among O and CO adsorbates can be quite different and significantly affect the binding energy of the adsorbates and, in turn, the dissociation energy⁴³. To further assess the latter point, we computed the activation energy of the dissociation reaction at different oxygen and hydrogen coverage in the supercell. As an example, we report the case of Cu in Figure 5. On one hand, the interaction of CO₂ with the surface turns out to be not affected by the higher coverage, given the weak interaction between CO₂ and the surface. On the other hand, both higher hydrogen (Figure 5b) and oxygen (Figure 5c) coverage causes an intense repulsion for CO and O and thus a destabilization of the final state of the reaction with respect to the case of a clean metal slab (Figure 5a). As a result, the dissociation reaction becomes more endothermic. Given the late character of the TS, the destabilization of the final state on the surface results in a destabilization of the transition state too and, correspondingly, the activation energy increases, as

evident by comparing the results obtained when CO₂ dissociates on a clean metal slab with those obtained when a both ¼ ML H and ¼ ML O coverages are present.

FIGURE 5

It is important to note that when the differences between the two competing pathways are small (as in the case of Cu) coverage effects may play a crucial role in determining the dominant reaction mechanism. For instance, by increasing the H coverage on Cu, CO₂ dissociation becomes more activated (2.20 eV) than hydrogenation (1.78 eV). On the whole, these results clearly show that the CO₂ dissociation barrier markedly depends on the relative stability of the products in the final state, which is mostly dominated by O. As the repulsion among adsorbates experienced in the final state increases, so does the CO₂ dissociation barrier.

We now consider the hydrogenation route to trans-COOH, which is the competitive pathway with respect to the dissociation reaction. Atomic hydrogen binds preferentially in a hollow site on all six metals, with a slight preference for the fcc site over the hcp site in all cases (see Table 2). As initial state for the CO₂ hydrogenation reaction we hence selected a configuration with a H atom occupying a fcc site and CO₂ weakly interacting with the metal surfaces. As final state of this reaction we consider the trans-COOH species, adsorbed through the C atom at a top site. In contrast to what observed for the dissociation route, we find that – despite of the same initial and final configurations – the geometry of the minimum energy path (MEP) for CO₂ hydrogenation changes among different metals. For instance, in the case of Pt, H diffuses to the top site before reacting with CO₂. On the Rh surface, instead, the H atom migrates towards the bridge site without going through the top site. As a consequence, the geometry of TS varies among the different metals, as shown in Figure 6.

FIGURE 6

The different MEP and the different TS among the metals are the results of the different contributions of reactants and products to the TS. In particular, in contrast to the CO₂ dissociation

reaction, initial state for the hydrogenation path shows a non-negligible interaction with the surface due to the presence of H, as evident from the values of binding energies reported in Table 2. In this situation, the formation of the TS is affected both by H (reactant) and t-COOH (product). As a first approximation, the relative difference between the binding energies of reactants and products can provide an estimation of the importance of reactants and products in determining the nature of the TS. Let us consider for instance the cases of Rh and Cu. On one hand, by going from Rh to Cu (see Table 2), t-COOH becomes 0.89 eV less stable, while H gets destabilized of 0.33 eV. On the other hand, CO₂ weakly interacts with the surface in both cases. As a consequence, the energy cost to form the TS becomes less dominated by t-COOH by going from Rh to Cu, and thus the character of the TS becomes more “early” (i.e., strongly influenced by the reactants) by going from Rh to Cu, as a result of the different interactions of reactants and products with the metal surface. This is consistent with the TS geometries reported in Figure 6. The TS on Cu resembles more the initial state (H and CO₂), whereas on Rh the TS has a geometry that is more similar to the product (t-COOH). For instance, for Rh, the C-metal distance is almost identical to the value in t-COOH in the final state (2.01 vs. 1.98 Å), whereas, for Cu, the C-metal distance is quite different from its value in t-COOH in the final state (2.34 vs. 1.97 Å). As a consequence of this change of the nature of the TS among the metals, the reaction does not closely obey the BEP principle, as shown in Figure 7. Therefore, we could not find a simple descriptor of the catalytic activity via the hydrogenation mechanism. Nonetheless, in sharp contrast with the competitive dissociation pathway, CO₂ hydrogenation to trans-COOH displays much less marked differences among the metals in terms of activation energy.

In conclusion, by the means of a systematic DFT analysis of the r-WGS reaction on Rh, Pt, Ni, Ag, Cu and Pd. (111) surfaces, we have provided compelling evidences that the change in affinity to oxygen among the different metals is the main cause to enable different dominant pathways for the CO₂ activation. In particular, COOH-mediated mechanism is favored on Pt, Ag and Pd, whereas Rh

Cu, and Ni dissociate CO₂ to CO and O, thus making the inverse of red-ox mechanism prevalent. We found that such a difference is related to a drastic change in the CO₂ dissociation barrier, which is not compensated by an equivalent variation in the hydrogenation activation energy. On one side, due to the late character of the transition state for the dissociation reaction and the very weak interaction of the CO₂ molecule with all the surfaces, the nature of the interaction between the adsorbed O and the surface is crucial in dictating the height of the CO₂ dissociation barrier. Specifically, the stronger is the metal-O interaction, the lower is the CO₂ dissociation barrier, thus making this route more favorable over the parallel hydrogenation route, which was found to be markedly less affected by the metal surface. As a result, the dominant reaction pathway for r-WGS changes among the metals and, in turn, a unique catalyst descriptor cannot be identified.

Acknowledgements

Computational time at CINECA-Fermi (Bologna, Italy) is gratefully acknowledged.

REFERENCES

- (1) Cox, P. M.; Betts, R. a; Jones, C. D.; Spall, S. a; Totterdell, I. J. *Nature* **2000**, *408*, 184–187.
- (2) Song, C. *Catal. Today* **2006**, *115*, 2–32.
- (3) Olah, G. a; Goeppert, A.; Prakash, G. K. S. *J. Org. Chem.* **2009**, *74*, 487–498.
- (4) Jentsch, M.; Trost, T.; Sterner, M. *Energy Procedia* **2014**, *46*, 254–261.
- (5) Cai, M.; Wen, J.; Chu, W.; Cheng, X.; Li, Z. *J. Nat. Gas Chem.* **2011**, *20*, 318–324.
- (6) Chang, F.-W.; Kuo, M.-S.; Tsay, M.-T.; Hsieh, M.-C. *Appl. Catal. A Gen.* **2003**, *247*, 309–320.
- (7) Karelovic, A.; Ruiz, P. *Appl. Catal. B Environ.* **2012**, *113-114*, 237–249.
- (8) Yu, K.-P.; Yu, W.-Y.; Kuo, M.-C.; Liou, Y.-C.; Chien, S.-H. *Appl. Catal. B Environ.* **2008**, *84*, 112–118.
- (9) Studt, F.; Abild-Pedersen, F.; Varley, J. B.; Nørskov, J. K. *Catal. Letters* **2012**, *143*, 71–73.
- (10) Cheng, D.; Negreiros, F. R.; Aprà, E.; Fortunelli, A. *ChemSusChem* **2013**, *6*, 944–965.
- (11) Grabow, L. C.; Gokhale, a. a.; Evans, S. T.; Dumesic, J. a.; Mavrikakis, M. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2008**, *112*, 4608–4617.
- (12) Gokhale, A. a; Dumesic, J. a; Mavrikakis, M. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2008**, *130*, 1402–1414.
- (13) Grabow, L. C.; Mavrikakis, M. *ACS Catal.* **2011**, *1*, 365–384.
- (14) Peng, G.; Sibener, S. J.; Schatz, G. C.; Mavrikakis, M. *Surf. Sci.* **2012**, *606*, 1050–1055.
- (15) Yang, Y.; Mims, C. a.; Mei, D. H.; Peden, C. H. F.; Campbell, C. T. *J. Catal.* **2013**, *298*, 10–17.
- (16) Hong, Q.-J.; Liu, Z.-P. *Surf. Sci.* **2010**, *604*, 1869–1876.
- (17) Meunier, F. C.; Tibiletti, D.; Goguet, a.; Shekhtman, S.; Hardacre, C.; Burch, R. *Catal. Today* **2007**, *126*, 143–147.
- (18) Kalamaras, C. M.; Panagiotopoulou, P.; Kondarides, D. I.; Efstathiou, A. M. *J. Catal.* **2009**, *264*, 117–129.
- (19) Jacobs, G.; Davis, B. H. *Appl. Catal. A Gen.* **2005**, *284*, 31–38.
- (20) Kalamaras, C. M.; Americanou, S.; Efstathiou, A. M. *J. Catal.* **2011**, *279*, 287–300.
- (21) Stamatakis, M.; Chen, Y.; Vlachos, D. G. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2011**, *115*, 24750–24762.

- (22) Maestri, M.; Reuter, K. *Chem. Eng. Sci.* **2012**, *74*, 296–299.
- (23) Liu, C.; Cundari, T. R.; Wilson, A. K. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2012**, *116*, 5681–5688.
- (24) Wang, G.-C.; Nakamura, J. *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2010**, *1*, 3053–3057.
- (25) Donazzi, a; Beretta, a; Groppi, G.; Forzatti, P. *J. Catal.* **2008**, *255*, 259–268.
- (26) Maestri, M.; Livio, D.; Beretta, A.; Groppi, G. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* **2014**, *53*, 10914–10928.
- (27) Peng, G.; Sibener, S. J.; Schatz, G. C.; Ceyer, S. T.; Mavrikakis, M. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2012**, *116*, 3001–3006.
- (28) Pekridis, G.; Kalimeri, K.; Kaklidis, N.; Vakouftsi, E.; Iliopoulou, E. F.; Athanasiou, C.; Marnellos, G. E. *Catal. Today* **2007**, *127*, 337–346.
- (29) Chen, C.; Cheng, W.; Lin, S. *Catal. Letters* **2000**, *68*, 45–48.
- (30) Vesselli, E.; Rizzi, M.; De Rogatis, L.; Ding, X.; Baraldi, A.; Comelli, G.; Savio, L.; Vattuone, L.; Rocca, M.; Fornasiero, P.; Baldereschi, A.; Peressi, M. *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2010**, *1*, 402–406.
- (31) Giannozzi, P.; Baroni, S.; Bonini, N.; Calandra, M.; Car, R.; Cavazzoni, C.; Ceresoli, D.; Chiarotti, G. L.; Cococcioni, M.; Dabo, I.; Dal Corso, A.; de Gironcoli, S.; Fabris, S.; Fratesi, G.; Gebauer, R.; Gerstmann, U.; Gougoussis, C.; Kokalj, A.; Lazzeri, M.; Martin-Samos, L.; Marzari, N.; Mauri, F.; Mazzarello, R.; Paolini, S.; Pasquarello, A.; Paulatto, L.; Sbraccia, C.; Scandolo, S.; Sclauzero, G.; Seitsonen, A. P.; Smogunov, A.; Umari, P.; Wentzcovitch, R. M. *J. Phys. Condens. Matter* **2009**, *21*, 395502.
- (32) Perdew, J. P.; Chevary, J. A.; Vosko, S. H.; Jackson, K. A.; Pederson, M. R.; Singh, D. J.; Fiolhais, C. *Phys. Rev. B* **1992**, *46*, 6671–6687.
- (33) Vanderbilt, D. *Phys. Rev. B* **1990**, *41*, 7892–7895.
- (34) Slater, J. C. *Phys. Rev.* **1936**, *49*, 537–545.
- (35) Henkelman, G.; Uberuaga, B. P.; Jónsson, H. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2000**, *113*, 9901.
- (36) Grimme, S.; Chemie, T. O.; Münster, O. I. D. U. **2006**, *16*.
- (37) Solymosi, F. *J. Mol. Catal.* **1991**, *65*.
- (38) Wang, S.-G.; Liao, X.-Y.; Cao, D.-B.; Huo, C.-F.; Li, Y.-W.; Wang, J.; Jiao, H. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2007**, *111*, 16934–16940.
- (39) Logadottir, a. *J. Catal.* **2001**, *197*, 229–231.
- (40) Bligaard, T.; Nørskov, J. K.; Dahl, S.; Matthiesen, J.; Christensen, C. H.; Sehested, J. *J. Catal.* **2004**, *224*, 206–217.
- (41) Gong, X.-Q.; Liu, Z.-P.; Raval, R.; Hu, P. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2004**, *126*, 8–9.

- (42) Lausche, A. C.; Medford, A. J.; Khan, T. S.; Xu, Y.; Bligaard, T.; Abild-Pedersen, F.; Nørskov, J. K.; Studt, F. *J. Catal.* **2013**, *307*, 275–282.
- (43) Bleakley, K.; Hu, P. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1999**, *121*, 7644–7652.

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Dissociation and COOH-mediated mechanisms.

Table 2: Species binding energies.

TABLES

Table 1.

Dissociation	COOH-mediated
1. $\text{CO}_2^* + * \rightarrow \text{CO}^* + \text{O}^*$	1. $\text{CO}_2^* + \text{H}^* \rightarrow \text{trans-COOH}^* + *$
2. $\text{O}^* + \text{H}^* \rightarrow \text{OH}^* + *$	2. $\text{trans-COOH}^* \rightarrow \text{cis-COOH}^*$
3. $\text{OH}^* + \text{H}^* \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O}^* + *$	3. $\text{cis-COOH}^* + * \rightarrow \text{CO}^* + \text{OH}^*$
	4. $\text{OH}^* + \text{H}^* \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O}^* + *$

Table 2.

metal species	Pt(111)		Rh(111)		Ni(111)	
	BE[eV]	site	BE[eV]	site	BE[eV]	site
CO ₂	-0.03	equivalent	-0.02	equivalent	-0.03	equivalent
CO ₂ metastable	0.47	top	0.32	top	0.35	top
CO	-1.79	hcp	-1.99	hcp	-1.85	hcp
O	-4.26	fcc	-5.18	fcc	-5.54	fcc
H	-2.73	fcc	-2.84	fcc	-2.78	fcc
trans-COOH	-2.32	top	-2.55	top	-2.29	top

metal species	Cu(111)		Ag(111)		Pd(111)	
	BE[eV]	site	BE[eV]	site	BE[eV]	site
CO ₂	-0.00	equivalent	-0.01	equivalent	-0.01	equivalent
CO ₂ metastable	-	not stable	-	not stable	-	not stable
CO	-0.90	fcc	-0.22	top	-2.02	hcp
O	-4.90	fcc	-3.68	fcc	-4.60	fcc
H	-2.51	fcc	-2.09	fcc	-2.87	fcc
trans-COOH	-1.66	top	-1.16	top	-2.20	top

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: dissociation (red column) and hydrogenation (black column) activation energies on Pt (111), Rh (111), Ni (111), Cu (111), Ag (111), Pd (111) metals.

Figure 2: dissociation (red line) and hydrogenation (black line) reaction paths on: panel (a) Pt (111); panel (b) Rh (111). The sign “∞” means non interacting adsorbate in the supercell.

Figure 3: lateral and upper view of the transition state structure for the dissociation reaction.

Figure 4: Brønsted-Evans-Polanyi relation for the CO₂ dissociation reaction ($\text{CO}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO} + \text{O}$).

Figure 5: activation energy of the dissociation step on Cu(111): panel (a) 0 ML, panel (b) ¼ ML of adsorbed hydrogen, panel (c) ¼ ML of adsorbed oxygen.

Figure 6: lateral and upper view of the transition state structure for the hydrogenation reaction.

Figure 7: Brønsted-Evans-Polanyi relation for the CO₂ hydrogenation reaction ($\text{CO}_2 + \text{H} \rightarrow \text{COOH}$)

FIGURES

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure 5

Figure 6.

Figure 7.

